

**THE EFFECT OF FOLIAR APPLICATION OF MICRO ELEMENT FERTILIZERS ON
COTTON FLOWERING DYNAMICS IN COTTON CULTIVATION**

¹Khahramonjon Davronov, ²Nodirbek Teshaboyev

¹Fergana Polytechnic Institute. Professor ²Independent researcher of Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8000859>

***Annotatsiya.** G'o'za o'simligini parvarishida uning gullash dinamikasi boshqa o'simliklardan mutlaqo farq qiladi. Ya'ni, gullash davri o'suv davri davomida doimiy ravishda birin ketinlik bilan gullab boradi. G'o'za navlarining gullash dinamikasini jadalligi avvalo uning biologik xususiyatlariga erta, o'rta va kech pisharligi yilning iqlim sharoitiga qolaversa qo'llanilgan agrotexnik tadbirlarning maqbul ta'siriga bog'liqdir*

***Kalit so'zlar:** mikroo'g'itlar, hosil, paxta, g'o'za, barg, biologik, gullash, suyuq, mineral.*

President Sh.Mirziyoyev in his 2021 address to the Parliament regarding the results of 2020, said that the huge changes being implemented in the agricultural system of our country, including agricultural reforms, the transfer of land areas to private clusters and cooperatives, will increase productivity in cotton production in one year. He noted that it was possible to increase the average by 10%, this year 91 thousand hectares of land were brought back into use, 133 thousand hectares or twice as much as last year, and water-saving technologies were introduced.

The President of Uzbekistan assigns the following responsibilities to every scientific worker to create opportunities for the growers of Uzbekistan and to put them into practice.

- rational use of land and water resources;
- maintaining and increasing the existing productivity of irrigated lands;
- development of agrotechnologies for obtaining high and quality crops from agricultural crops;

Based on these tasks, we plan to make full use of existing agro-technologies in the field of cotton cultivation and to conduct scientific and practical research in their application and to widely apply them to production.

Different mineral and organic fertilizers are used in the required amount so that the microelements in the soil can be well absorbed by the plant. In order to increase the productivity of cotton, based on the study and determination of the periods of application of liquid NPK fertilizers in plant nutrition, the productivity of cotton crops in the soil and climate of Fergana region is at least 4-5 determines that the increase to s/ha is the main urgent issue.

Today, cotton yield increases by 12-19% as a result of using microfertilizers in various ways and periods in the cultivation of cotton raw materials around the world [1].

In the conditions of our republic, it is important to carry out scientific and practical research on the development and practical use of macro and micro fertilizers by chemical scientists and to develop specific recommendations and suggestions based on them. .

When caring for cotton, its flowering dynamics are completely different from other plants. That is, during the flowering period, it blooms continuously throughout the growing season. In other plants, it blooms once and the crop ripens uniformly in the specified period.

The rapidity of flowering dynamics of cotton varieties depends first of all on its biological characteristics (early, medium and late ripening), climatic conditions of the year, as well as on the optimal effect of applied agrotechnical measures [2].

The characteristics of the surface of the leaves of the S-8290 cotton variety, the dynamics of the opening of the flowering pods when liquid NPK fertilizers and the fertilizer composed of trace elements known as Kafolon were applied through the leaves were determined in the research. . Because fertilizers in this condition not only allow the growth of cotton, but also accelerate the ripening period. Scientific data obtained in this regard are presented in Table 3.7-3.8.

It should be noted that the dynamics of cotton flowering was determined in the 2nd repetition of each option every 2-3 days after 20-30% flowering.

Mineral fertilizers were applied at the rate of N130, P90, K65 kg/ha (1-4) and 28.2% of the options and 26.9% on average entered the flower after two days. the indicators were found to be 47.6 and 49.0%, respectively, the average was 48.3%, and after 5 days, the average was 68.4%. We would like to emphasize another case that in the conditions of 2021, if the seed was sown on April 12, 96 days later, 68.4% of the cotton in the control variant was observed to have flowered. In order to accelerate cotton flowering, i.e., for faster ripening of the crop, due to the accumulation of microelements in liquid state applied through the leaves, the average of 32.3 out of 2 returns in proportion to the observation periods; It was determined that 56.1 and 76.4% of the plants were in flower. These indicators are 5.4 proportionally higher than the control; 7.8 and 8.0% higher.

The reason for the increase in cotton flowering in this and other variants is that when microelements and liquid NPK fertilizers are applied through the leaves, the surface of the leaf surface increases, the photosynthesis process accelerates, and as a result, the development of cotton improves. blooms faster. But this situation also depends on the optimal effect of the norms of applied mineral fertilizers.

Against the background of the standards of mineral fertilizers N130, P90, K65 kg/ha, liquid NPK and micronutrients were 34.3 in the period of observation when applied through the leaves 3 times during the periods of cotton development; It was observed that 59.5 and 79.8% of the plants were in flower. These indicators are 7.4 proportionally higher than those of the control option; 10.9 and 11.4% higher, as well as 2.0 compared to option 2, where only micronutrient accumulation was used; 3.1 and 3.4% are more.

When the fertilizer called Kafolon, which contains microelements that dissolve well in water, was applied through the leaves for the 4th time, the indicators were 8.9 compared to the control; increased by 9.0 and 9.4%, but 0.5 due to the effect of liquid NPK + trace elements; It was found that it was less by 1.9 and 2.0%.

So, against the background of mineral fertilizers N130, P90, K65 kg/ha, it was observed that all types of microelements and liquid NPK fertilizers applied through leaves have an acceptable effect on increasing the level of flowering of cotton.

Mineral fertilizers N180, P125, K90 kg/ha were used in the control of options (5-8), the flowering levels of cotton were 27.5 in proportion to the observation periods; It was found that it was 49.8 and 66.1%. These indicators are 0.6 more than those of the control (1) option in background I; 1.5 and 0.7% more, these differences were calculated due to the increase in the norm of mineral fertilizers.

It should be noted that with an increase in the rate of mineral fertilizers from N130, P90, K65 kg/ha to N180, P125, K90 kg/ha, cotton flowering levels increased by 0.6-1.5% It was

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found that this process increased by 8.0-9.4% at the end of observation (23.07) when NPK and microelements were applied in suspension through leaves.

In the background of mineral fertilizers N180, P125, K90 kg/ha, when liquid micronutrient fertilizers are applied as a suspension through cotton leaves 3 times (6 options), the degree of cotton flowering is proportional to the observation periods (average of 2 returns) 33.4; 58.4 and 78.2%, 5.9 from the control; 8.6 and 9.1% were found to be excessive. In addition, it was observed that these figures were 1.8% more than those of the 2nd option at the end of the observation.

In the experiment, relatively acceptable data on the increase in the flowering level of cotton were obtained when the liquid fertilizer containing NPK and microelements was applied 3 times through the leaves (7 options), and in proportion to the observation periods, 35.2; 61.2; It was 82.1%. These indicators are 8.1 more than the control; By 11.4 and 13.0%, it was found to be 2.3% more than that of the parallel (3) option in the I background.

Fertilizers called Kafolon containing liquid microelements were applied 4 times during cotton development periods (the last one was at bud bearing) and in the 8th variant, the flowering levels in proportion to the observation periods were 34.6 on average from 2 returns. ; 60.0 and 79.8% of the control, 7.1; 10.2 and 10.7% higher, but acceptable (7) compared to 1.0; It was observed that it was less by 0.2 and 2.3%.

Mineral fertilizers N230, P160, K115 kg/ha were used in the control of options (9-12), the dynamics of cotton flowering was 23.8; 49.3 and 66.1%, it was observed that it was 1.0% less than the control in the II background, and 0.3% less than the control in the I background.

Therefore, it was determined that liquid NPK and a set of micronutrients should be applied 3 times through the leaves against the background of mineral fertilizers N180, P125, K90 kg/ha, to accelerate the flowering rate of cotton by 13.0% compared to the control.

Table 1

Effect of foliar application of micronutrient mineral fertilizers on cotton flowering dynamics, (%), 2021

Option order	Annual rates of mineral fertilizers, kg/ha			Mineral fertilizers with microelements, ml, l/ha	18.07		Average	20.07		Average	23.07		Average
					returns			returns			returns		
	N	P	K	I	III	I	III	I	III				
1	130	90	65	–	25,6	28,2	26,9	47,6	49,0	48,3	69,3	67,5	68,4
2	130	90	65	Liquid microelements	31,8	32,8	32,3	55,8	56,4	56,1	77,5	75,3	76,4
3	130	90	65	Liquid NPK and trace elements	33,5	35,1	34,3	58,9	59,5	59,2	81,2	78,4	79,8
4	130	90	65	Kafolon	32,6	35,0	33,8	56,5	58,1	57,3	78,6	77,0	77,8

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5	180	125	90	–	26,5	28,5	27,5	48,4	51,2	49,8	64,9	68,3	69,1
6	180	125	90	Liquid micro-elements	33,0	33,8	33,4	59,1	57,7	58,4	79,1	77,3	78,2
7	180	125	90	Liquid NPK and trace elements	34,8	36,4	35,6	60,1	62,4	61,2	82,1	82,1	82,1
8	180	125	90	Kafolon	33,6	35,6	34,6	60,0	60,0	60,0	81,3	78,3	79,8
9	230	160	115	–	22,8	34,8	23,8	48,4	52,2	49,3	68,5	67,6	68,1
10	230	160	115	Liquid micro-elements	32,1	33,9	33,0	56,8	57,4	57,1	80,1	78,3	79,2
11	230	160	115	Liquid NPK and trace elements	34,3	35,7	35,0	59,6	60,5	60,1	80,3	76,3	79,3
12	230	160	115	Kafolon	32,0	34,2	33,1	58,9	59,8	59,1	80,2	77,6	78,9

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